

OPTIMIZATION OF THERMAL TREATMENT METHODS FOR LOCAL PROCUREMENT OF INDUSTRIAL BEARING MATERIALS.

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Annotation. The selection is based on the way they are used, taking into account the variety of casting methods. Of course, as we continue our scientific work, we will focus more on the injection molding method.

Keywords: bearing details, ring, casting method, material, shaft, hardness, content, vacuum, impact viscosity.

Introduction

High-carbon chromium steel is mainly used in the production of bearing rings. Based on this, the cast part is obtained and the next stage is the mechanical processing.

On an industrial scale, there are a number of methods for casting liquid metals or alloys into special casting methods.

Material and Methods

Not all grades of steel can be considered serviceable without heat treatment, especially of bearing component materials. The depth of penetration of such bearing steels is considered large. Thermal treatment plays a key role in achieving the desired result.

Thus, ShX15 is a very unique material with a number of unique physical properties. These properties allow it to be used in various industrial and engineering fields.

1 pic. Machining process on a lathe

Through this, you can get the necessary hardness. In addition, the impact viscosity should be high and the level of resistance to eating should be in place. In order to obtain such a quality material, it is necessary to ensure that the carbide is not unevenly distributed, and to achieve this, it is necessary to cast by vacuum method. Such steels are produced in the form of rods or tubes shown above.

Results

The properties of steel products improve as a result of thermal and chemical-thermal treatments. In practice, products are subjected to the following thermal treatments depending on their age, material and expected properties.

1 pic. Process of heat treatment of steels

Softening. It is known that in the production of castings of complex shape, if the internal tensile stresses are added to the external forces acting on them during the working process, cracks may appear. Therefore, such castings are softened in order to relieve internal stress and improve their structure. According to the shape, size and other parameters of the casting, the furnace is selected and the softening mode is determined. For example, average castings are gradually heated to a temperature of 500-550°C, and after holding at this temperature for several hours, they are cooled together with the furnace. During rapid cooling of castings in a metal mold, in most cases, the hardness of the surface layer increases excessively. This creates difficulties in cutting. Therefore, in order to reduce the surface hardness of such castings, they are also softened.

Discussion

Normalize. It is normalized in order to increase the precision and plasticity of castings. For this purpose, castings are heated up to 850-900°C, after holding at this temperature for a certain time, they are cooled in air. It is known that when the casting is heated to 850-900°C, the free graphite in its content dissolves in austenite. When this casting is cooled in air, the amount of perlite increases and its grains are crushed.

Find out. The purpose of finding castings is to improve their accuracy. For this, the ingot is heated to 850-900°C, kept at this temperature for a certain time, then cooled in water, oil or salt solution. The resulting cast structure consists of martensite, residual austenite and graphite.

Release. It is released in order to free the casts from internal stress. The release mode is determined by the expected hardness. If higher hardness is required, it is released at low 200-250°C, if lower hardness is required, at high 450-600°C. In order to increase the precision, hardness, corrosion resistance of castings and make them resistant to corrosion, chemical and thermal treatments are also given.

Conclusion

ShX15 steel is a heat-resistant and corrosion-resistant material that is widely used in various industries. It belongs to the class of high alloy steels and has many unique physical properties.

One of the most important physical properties of ShX15 is its high thermal stability. This material can withstand very high temperatures, which can be used in equipment that requires high temperatures. In addition, it has excellent mechanical properties such as strength and corrosion resistance, which make it suitable for high-load or friction applications.

In addition, ShX15 has low thermal conductivity and low electrical conductivity, which makes it suitable for use in various electronic and electrical equipment.

3 pic. ShX15 steel material.

In general, ShX15 steel is a very unique material with a number of unique physical properties. These properties make it suitable for use in various industrial and engineering fields. It can withstand high temperatures, has excellent mechanical properties, is distinguished from other materials by high corrosion resistance and low electrical conductivity.

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